

**ASSESSING THE FREQUENCY OF UNREPORTED BULLYING AND
VICTIMIZATION AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
AT ALCANTARA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to uncover unreported bullying and victimization among junior high school students at Alcantara National High School, focusing on their frequency, types, locations, and reporting habits. Using a descriptive research design, 242 students from Grades 7 to 10 participated in a survey conducted through a researcher-developed questionnaire. The results revealed a prevalent pattern of bullying experiences, with 74% of students reporting victimization. Verbal bullying was the most common form of unreported incidents (29%), followed by social (25%), physical (20%), and cyberbullying (11%). Notably, classrooms emerged as frequent sites for unreported bullying when teachers were not in the classrooms (71%). Students displayed diverse reporting preferences, with 51% confiding in friends, 22% in parents, and 15% in class advisers. Among unreported victims, slightly more were females (52%), notably concentrated in Grade 7 (57%) and Grade 10 (53%). The study highlighted fluctuating bullying trends across grades, peaking in Grade 10, emphasizing the need for tailored interventions to address unreported incidents and the diverse experiences of victimization. These findings advocate for comprehensive strategies that create a safer and more supportive learning environment at Alcantara National High School.

Keywords: *Unreported; Bullying; Victimization; Junior high school*

INTRODUCTION

Bullying or peer abuse is described as intentional, hostile behavior intended towards a specific victim who may be outnumbered, younger, weaker, disabled, or otherwise vulnerable (DepEd Order No. 40, series 2012). The most frequently reported cases to the guidance office at Alcantara National High School—Junior High School (ANHS-JHS) are bullying and victimization. On September 30, 2022, the designated school guidance advocate documented the first bullying incident involving physical violence committed by a male student in grade 10 section Diamond against a male student in grade 10 section Sapphire. This event resulted in bodily harm. On October 5, 2022, a similar bullying incident involving physical violence was reported to the guidance office. Another male student from grade 10 section Sapphire engaged in physical bullying against the victim, a student from grade 9 section Venus, resulting in physical injury. These two incidents of bullying occurred following school dismissal and outside of the school's boundaries.

While on October 6, 2022, two bullies and one victim of verbal bullying were reported to the guidance office, on October 18, 2022, one more bully and one victim of physical bullying were reported, and on October 27, 2022, two bullies and one victim of bullying were reported, this incident occurred on the school campus during a period of vacancy. On November 15, 2022, the guidance office received one report of bullying involving one bully and one victim. Four bullies and one victim of cyberbullying were reported to the guidance office in January 2023, along with two bullies and two victims of physical bullying.

Bullying and victimization can have significant effects on the academic and social outcomes of junior high school students. According to research, students who experience bullying are more likely to miss school, to have lower academic achievement, and to experience social withdrawal (Espelage & Swearer, 2013). In addition, the psychological effects of bullying can persist into adulthood and cause long-term mental health problems (Bradshaw et al., 2007).

Despite efforts to combat bullying, research indicates that many instances of bullying and victimization continue to go unreported, especially among junior high school students. Underreporting is caused by several factors, including fear of retaliation, shame, and a lack of trust in school authorities (Zych et al., 2017). The frequency of unreported bullying and victimization among junior high school students at Alcantara National High School must be determined in order to develop effective interventions.

This study is the first investigation into the frequency with which bullying and victimization go unreported at Alcantara National High School Junior High School. There haven't been any studies done at Alcantara National High School before that specifically looked at how frequent it is for junior high school students to be bullied or victimized without reporting it. This research fills in the gap in the frequency of unreported bullying and victimization at Alcantara National High School. By assessing the frequency of unreported bullying and victimization, this study holds the key to understanding an overlooked aspect of student experiences. The findings are poised to be instrumental in shaping an intervention program tailored to address these

unreported incidents, thereby fostering a safer and more supportive environment for the students at Alcantara National High School-Junior High School.

Research Questions

1. What is the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to sex and grade level?
 2. What is the unreported frequency and percentage of distribution of the respondents per grade level according to their experience of being bullied?
 3. What are the common forms of bullying experience by the respondents who were unreported bullied/victim in school?
 4. What is the summary of the respondents' ratings on the common forms of bullying experienced by the respondents who were unreported bullied or victim in school?
 5. What is the unreported frequency of respondents' responses to the location or place where bullying usually happens?
 6. To whom thus unreported bullying in school usually reported by the respondents?
 7. What is the unreported profile of victim according to grade level and sex?
 8. What are the unreported characteristics of the bully?
 9. What recommendation can be made to address the frequency of unreported bullying and victimization assessed in this study?
 10. What future studies can be made based on the findings of the study?
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METHODOLOGY

The descriptive research design was used as the methodological approach in this basic research. The methodology was applied to the demographic parameters of the participants in order to assess the frequency of unreported bullying and victimization among junior high school students at Alcantara National High School.

The sample population consisted of junior high school students, who were selected using a simple random sampling technique. Each student in the population had an equal probability of being chosen for the sample. The survey research utilized the RaoSoft online sample size calculator in order to determine the necessary sample size for achieving statistically valid results. The sample was determined using a random number generator.

As teacher-researchers, we obtained formal approval from the ANHS principal to conduct basic research on the relevant students at ANHS-JHS. We administered the structured survey questionnaire, a quantitative data collection instrument, to 242 students out of the total 281 respondents in Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10. A structured survey questionnaire was employed to gather data for this study. The questionnaire consisted of 22 questions pertaining to the study's objective. The survey questions for this study were based on the OBQ Standard School Report (Olweus Bullying Questionnaire Standard School Report, 2007) as a reference in framing the questions for this study. The content validity of the instrument was assessed through a validation process involving multiple individuals from Alcantara National High School. These individuals included the Head Teacher II of Mathematics, the Research Coordinator, a Master Teacher I who teaches research subjects, and three additional

Filipino subject teachers from the Filipino Department. The instrument was pilot-tested at Tugdan National High School, Alcantara, Romblon.

The instrument yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .823 when administered to items 1 to 10. Furthermore, the analysis of bullying occurrences as indicated by items 16 to 22 demonstrated a heightened degree of internal reliability, supported by a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .903.

RESULTS

Table 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents according to Sex and Grade Level

Sex	Grade				Total
	Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	
Female	31 (54%)	39 (54%)	17 (45%)	46 (61%)	133 (55%)
Male	26 (46%)	33 (46%)	21 (55%)	29 (39%)	109 (45%)
Total	57 (24%)	72 (30%)	38 (16%)	75 (30%)	242(100%)

Table 2

Unreported Frequency and Percentage of Distribution of the Respondents per Grade Level according to their Experience of Being Bullied

	Grade Occurrence of Bullying				Total
	Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	
Never been bullied	8 (14%)	19 (26%)	16 (42%)	20 (27%)	63 (26%)
Bullied/Victim	49 (86%)	53 (74%)	22 (58%)	55 (73%)	179 (74%)
Total	57 (100%)	72 (100%)	38 (100%)	75 (100%)	242 (100%)

Figure 1

Common Forms of Bullying Experience by the Respondents who were Unreported Bullied/Victim in School

Table 4

Summary of the Respondents' Ratings on the Common Forms of Bullying Experienced by the Respondents who were Bullied in School

Forms of Bullying	Frequency (% of Total)
A. Verbal Bullying	214 (29%)
Name calling, teasing, taunting	122 (17%)
Sexual comments	92 (12%)
B. Social Bullying	183 (25%)
Social exclusion, isolation	54 (7%)
Spreading rumors or lies	74 (10%)
Things taken away or damaged	55 (8%)
C. Physical Bullying	146 (20%)
Kicked, shoved, hit, slap	95 (13%)
Threatened or forced to do bad things	51 (7%)
D. Cyber-bullying	77 (11%)
E. Others	109 (15%)

Figure 2

Location or Place Where Bullying Usually Happens

Figure 3

Person/s whom bullying is usually reported by the victims

Table 5

Unreported Profile of Victim according to Grade Level and Sex

Grade Level	Female	Male	Total
7	28 (57%)	21 (43%)	49 (27%)
8	28 (53%)	25 (47%)	53 (30%)
9	8 (36%)	14 (64%)	22 (12%)
10	29 (53%)	26 (47%)	55 (31%)
Total	93 (52%)	86 (48%)	179 (100%)

Table 6

Unreported Characteristics of the Bully

Characteristics	Frequency
A. Class or Grade Level	
The same grade level (classmates)	158 (88%)
Higher grade level	17 (10%)
Lower grade level	4 (2%)
Total	179 (100%)
B. Sex composition of Bullies	
Several boys	92 (51%)
Several girls	68 (38%)
One girl	19 (11%)
Total	179 (100%)
C. Number of students who do the bullying	
Mainly by one student	98 (55%)
A group of 2 to 3 students	73 (41%)
A group of 4 to 9 students	6 (3%)
A group of more than nine students	2 (1%)
Total	179 (100%)

DISCUSSION

1. The researcher performed statistical analysis to evaluate the demographic characteristics of the research sample, specifically focusing on sex and grade level. Descriptive statistics, including counts and percentages, were employed to present a comprehensive depiction of the distribution of male and female participants across different grade levels. Table 1 illustrates the frequency distribution of the respondents, classified according to their sex and grade level. The sample of 242 respondents showed a sex assigned at birth distribution of 55% females and 45% males. Grade 8 had 30% representation, Grade 10 had 30%, Grade 7 had 24%, and Grade 9 had 16%. Notably, in Grade 7, females comprised 54%, in Grade 8, 54% were females, in Grade 9, 45% were females, and in Grade 10, 61% were females. This research offers a comprehensive view of respondent distribution by sex assigned at birth and grade level.

2. The researcher utilized statistical analysis to investigate the frequency of bullying incidents among respondents across various grade levels. Descriptive statistics, including percentages and counts, were employed to provide an in-depth assessment of the distribution of respondents who experienced bullying or victimization and those who did not. Table 2 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents per grade level who have encountered bullying but have not reported it. The data highlights prevalent bullying experiences: 86% and 74% of Grade 7 and 8 respondents encountered bullying, with only 14% and 26%, respectively, reporting no instances. In Grade 9, 58% reported bullying, while Grade 10 had 73%. Overall, 74% of the sample faced bullying. Notably, Grades 7 and 8 exhibited higher bullying rates, aligning with Ahmad and Smith's 2022 study emphasizing elevated bullying among Grade 7 students.

3. The researcher employed descriptive statistics, specifically percentages, to analyze the percentage of different forms of bullying among unreported victims. The researcher analyzed the percentage of students who experienced various forms of unreported victimization, including verbal, social, physical, and cyberbullying. Figure 1 illustrates the most common types of bullying experienced by respondents who were victims of bullying in school settings but chose not to disclose the incidents. Figure 1 shows unreported victim experiences: 29% verbal, 25% social, 20% physical, 11% cyberbullying, and 15% categorized as "others." This aligns with Shahrour et al.'s 2020 study, highlighting verbal bullying as predominant among adolescents, reported by victims and those in dual bully-victim roles.

4. The researcher used descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentage to analyze the reported frequency of common types of bullying among the participants. Table 4 presents a summary of the ratings provided by respondents who experienced bullying in school regarding the common forms of bullying they encountered. The data portrays a comprehensive view of bullying forms and their prevalence among respondents. Verbal bullying emerges as the most prevalent category at 29%, with name calling, teasing, and taunting constituting 17% and sexual comments at 12%. Social bullying accounts for 25%, prominently involving spreading rumors or lies (10%), social exclusion or isolation (7%), and instances of belongings taken or damaged (8%). Physical bullying, reported at 20%, manifests predominantly through

acts like kicking, shoving, hitting, or slapping (13%), and coercion into unethical actions (7%). Cyber-bullying stands at 11%. Additionally, a category labeled as "Others" encompasses 15% of reported incidents, signifying less specified forms of bullying. The findings align with Arifuddin et al. (2021), illustrating verbal bullying through taunting, physical humiliation, mockery, and derogatory language. Sterzing et al. (2020) support predominant physical bullying acts: pushing, shoving, hitting, or slapping. Additionally, Tran, Weiss, and Nguyen (2022) highlight high-schoolers' increased participation in maladaptive cyber-interactions, linked to heightened internet usage.

5. The researcher used descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and percentage, to analyze the common locations of bullying incidents reported by the respondents. Figure 2 displays the undisclosed frequency of participants' responses concerning the specific locations or areas where instances of bullying commonly take place within school settings. A significant proportion of respondents (71%) reported that instances of bullying frequently occur within the classroom setting in the absence of the teacher. Furthermore, a total of 13% of the respondents indicated instances of bullying taking place in areas such as the playground, open court, stage, or gate. Additional areas, such as corridors, stairways, lobbies, comfort rooms/bathrooms, and canteens, were identified by a minority of respondents, with proportions ranging from 1% to 6%. The findings affirm the study by (Borualogo, I. S., Wahyudi, H., & Kusdiyati, S., 2020) that the majority of bullying instances, constituting 76.2% of reported cases, occurred specifically within the classroom environment.

6. The researcher used descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and percentage, to analyze the reporting patterns of unreported bullying incidents among the respondents.

Figure 3 depicts the typical individual to whom respondents commonly disclose their experiences of being bullied within a school setting. Survey results showed 51% of respondents disclosed unreported bullying to friends, while 22% reported to parents or guardians. Class advisers or subject teachers were chosen by 15%, and 6% mentioned siblings as potential recipients. One respondent reported to a school guidance advocate, and 3% mentioned alternatives like cousins or on-duty guards. These findings align with Coyle, Malecki, and Emmons' (2021) research, emphasizing the crucial role of peer support networks among adolescents, specifically high school students who predominantly seek and value assistance, understanding, and companionship from their peers during this developmental stage, often prioritizing this form of support over others.

7. Descriptive statistics were utilized by the researcher for data analysis. The study conducted a frequency count of unreported victims in each grade level and calculated percentages to assess the distribution of males and females within each grade level. Table 5 presents the distribution of victim profiles based on their grade level and sex, which has not been previously reported. In total, 52% of the 179 affected students were female, and 48% were male. In Grade 7, 57% of the 49 unreported victims were female, while Grade 8 had 53% female victims out of 53. Grade 9 had 36% female victims out of 22, and Grade 10 showed a near-even split, with females at 53% out of 55 total reported instances.

8. Descriptive statistics were employed by the researcher to analyze and present the frequency and percentage of respondents' responses pertaining to the characteristics of the bully. Rankings were employed to emphasize the hierarchical position, thereby highlighting particular characteristics of a bully. Table 6 displays the undisclosed characteristics of individuals involved in bullying conduct. The majority of bullies, 88% of the incidents, were classmates. Fewer perpetrators were from higher (10%) or lower (2%) grade levels. These findings align with Salavera et al.'s (2021) research, where 24% admitted to bullying classmates, and 39% identified themselves as targets. Male students accounted for 51% of reported bullying incidents, indicating their higher frequency as perpetrators, followed by females at 38%. In 11% of cases, a single female was identified as a perpetrator. These findings align with Nurulwahida et al.'s (2022) research, highlighting male students' more frequent involvement in bullying, potentially linked to their emphasis on physical attributes. In 55% of bullying cases, a single student was primarily responsible, emphasizing individual perpetrators. Incidents involving 2 to 3 students comprised 41%, while a minority involved larger groups: 4-9 students (3%) or over 9 students (1%).

Conclusions

1. The study included 242 participants, with females comprising 55% and males 45% of the sample. Grade 8 showed the highest respondent rate, followed by Grade 10, while the remainder consisted of students from Grade 7 and Grade 9. This distribution indicates a higher representation from Grade 8 and Grade 10 compared to the other grade levels within the sample.
2. A study examining bullying victimization among Grade 7 to 10 students revealed varying incidences across grades. Among Grade 7 and 8 participants, 86% reported experiencing bullying. Specifically, Grade 8 initially recorded a 74% incidence, which notably decreased to 58% in Grade 9. However, the frequency surged in Grade 10, reaching 73%. This suggests a fluctuating trend in bullying experiences, peaking in Grade 10 compared to the other grades surveyed.
3. Unreported victims in school encounter diverse forms of bullying, spanning verbal, social, physical, and cyberbullying. A substantial proportion of these unreported incidents falls under the umbrella category labeled as "others," denoting the existence of additional unidentified types of bullying.
4. Among victims who chose not to report incidents of bullying, verbal bullying emerged as the predominant form.
5. Classroom bullying often occurs when the teacher is not present, as reported by the majority of respondents. Bullying has been observed in multiple areas, such as the playground, open court, stage, gate, corridors, stairways, lobbies, restrooms, and canteens.
6. Respondents generally disclose unreported experiences with bullying to friends, parents or guardians, class advisers or subject teachers, and siblings.

7. The data indicates that a slightly higher percentage of female students fell victim among the unreported victims. The highest percentage of unreported victims was found among students in Grade 7, followed by those in Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10.

8. The majority of bullies were identified as classmates of their targets. The frequency of bullying was highest among male students, with female students exhibiting a similar level of occurrence. Most bullying incidents are committed by a single student, although a notable proportion of cases involve a group consisting of 2 to 3 students.

Recommendations

1. ANHS-JHS administrator may prioritize anti-bullying programs that increase awareness and education among students, teachers, and parents. These programs may cover various forms of bullying, its consequences, and effective strategies for prevention and intervention.

2. ANHS-JHS administrator, head teachers, master teachers, teachers and guidance advocate-designate may enhance reporting mechanisms: It is imperative to establish transparent and easily accessible channels for students to report incidents of bullying.

3. ANHS-JHS administrator, head teachers, master teachers, teachers and guidance advocate-designate may improve supervision and monitoring. It is important for teachers and school administrator to be diligent in overseeing areas that are frequently associated with bullying, such as classrooms, playgrounds, and other designated areas. Effective supervision during breaks and transitions can serve as a deterrent to bullying and facilitate timely intervention when needed.

4. ANHS-JHS administrator may hire expert or registered guidance counselor (RGC) for proper counseling and support services for individuals involved in bullying incidents, including both victims and perpetrators.

5. Collaboration between School Governing Council and Parent-Teachers Association is crucial for effectively addressing bullying. ANHS-JHS administrator, teachers and guidance advocate-designate may actively involve parents in various ways, such as regular communication and participation in anti-bullying initiatives.

6. Future researchers may investigate the impact of Alcantara National High School's intervention on reducing instances of bullying and victimization among junior high school students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to initiating the basic research, the researchers sought parental consent from the parents/guardians of student participants, ensuring that it was obtained

willingly, with prior awareness, and after providing comprehensive information. Participants were assured that their identities and personal information would remain anonymous and confidential, and that the collected data would be used solely for research purposes.

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